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Urbanization And Food Security In Bayelsa State, Nigeria

¹Akarara, Ebierinyo Ayebaemi and ²Omidiji, Adedoyin Oluwatoyin

¹Department of Economics,
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
ebierinyoakarara@ndu.edu.ng +234-7037892022 ; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1591-1141>

²Department of Geography and Environmental Management
Faculty of Social Sciences,
Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, Nigeria
adedoyinomidiji@ndu.edu.ng; +234-8036686301 ; <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9634-6927>

Corresponding author - adedoyinomidiji@ndu.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of urbanization on household food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, with particular attention to socio-economic, environmental, and market factors. Using a cross-sectional survey design, data were collected from 438 households across the three senatorial districts, and analyzed using descriptive statistics and a logit regression model. The results indicate that urbanization significantly reduces the probability of households being food secure ($\beta = -0.542$, $dy/dx = -0.126$), reflecting pressures on food availability, access, and stability in rapidly urbanizing areas. Socio-economic factors including household income, employment status, and education positively influence food security, increasing the likelihood of being food secure by 15.5%, 9.0%, and 11.8%, respectively. Environmental challenges such as flooding significantly reduce food security ($dy/dx = -0.142$), while access to land ($dy/dx = 0.101$) and better market access ($dy/dx = 0.088$) improve household resilience. Higher food prices are associated with decreased food security ($dy/dx = -0.108$). These findings highlight the multidimensional nature of food security in urbanizing regions and underscore the need for integrated policies that address urban growth, livelihood support, environmental resilience, and market stabilization.

Keywords: Urbanization, Food Security, Household Socio-Economic Factors, Environmental Challenges, Market Access

1. INTRODUCTION

Urbanization has become one of the most defining demographic and economic transformations of the 21st century, particularly in developing countries. Globally, the urban population has expanded rapidly, with projections indicating that more than two-thirds of the world's population will reside in urban areas by 2050 (United Nations, 2015). This rapid urban expansion has been especially pronounced in Sub-Saharan Africa, where cities are growing at unprecedented rates, often outpacing the capacity of infrastructure and social services (FAO, 2008). While urbanization is frequently associated with economic opportunities and structural transformation, it also presents significant challenges, particularly in relation to food security, poverty, and environmental sustainability (Satterthwaite & Mitlin, 2012; Godschalk, 2003).

Food security, defined as access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food for an active and healthy life (FAO, 2008), has evolved from a narrow focus on food availability to a broader, multidimensional

concept encompassing access, utilization, and stability (Barrett, 2010; Clapp, 2015). In recent decades, the discourse on food security has increasingly shifted toward urban contexts due to the growing incidence of urban poverty and food insecurity (Haddad et al., 1999; Maxwell, 1999). Urban food systems are characterized by complex supply chains, heavy reliance on market purchases, and vulnerability to price shocks, making urban households particularly susceptible to food insecurity despite their proximity to food markets (Crush & Frayne, 2011; Battersby, 2013).

In Nigeria, urbanization has accelerated significantly over the past few decades, driven by rural–urban migration, population growth, and economic restructuring. However, this rapid urban expansion has not been matched by commensurate improvements in employment opportunities, housing, or food systems. Consequently, many urban residents, particularly those in informal settlements, face persistent challenges related to food access, affordability, and nutritional quality. Despite the country’s substantial agricultural potential, food insecurity remains widespread, reflecting structural inefficiencies in food production, distribution, and income generation (Salahudeen et al., 2024).

Bayelsa State, located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria, presents a unique context for examining the nexus between urbanization and food security. The state is characterized by rapid urban growth, ecological vulnerability, and heavy dependence on oil-related activities, which have contributed to the neglect of agriculture and local food systems. Additionally, recurrent flooding, environmental degradation, and limited arable land further constrain food production and accessibility. Empirical evidence from the state indicates that factors such as high food prices, low income levels, unemployment, and environmental shocks significantly influence household food security outcomes (Elum & Digitemie, 2023).

Moreover, the urbanization process in Bayelsa State has intensified pressures on existing food systems by increasing demand for food while simultaneously reducing local agricultural production. This imbalance often leads to greater dependence on imported food from other regions, thereby exposing urban households to supply disruptions and price volatility. The interplay between urban expansion, environmental challenges, and socio-economic constraints underscores the complexity of food security issues in the state.

Although a growing body of literature has examined food security in Nigeria and other developing countries, studies that explicitly explore the relationship between urbanization and food security at the sub-national level, particularly in the Niger Delta region, remain limited. Existing research has largely focused on rural food security, agricultural productivity, or national-level analyses, leaving a critical gap in understanding how urbanization dynamics influence food systems and household welfare in rapidly urbanizing states such as Bayelsa.

Against this backdrop, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between urbanization and food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. Specifically, it aims to examine how urban growth patterns affect food availability, accessibility, and affordability, as well as to identify the socio-economic and environmental factors that mediate this relationship. By providing empirical insights into the urban food security nexus, the study contributes to the broader discourse on sustainable urban development and offers policy-relevant recommendations for enhancing food security in rapidly urbanizing regions. The broad objective of this study is to examine the relationship between urbanization and food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the effect of urbanization on household food security in Bayelsa State, with particular emphasis on food availability, access, utilization, and stability.
2. Examine the socio-economic determinants of food security among urban households, including income levels, employment status, household size, and education.
3. Evaluate the impact of environmental factors associated with urbanization such as flooding, land degradation, and loss of agricultural land on food production and accessibility in the state.
4. Analyze the role of urban food systems and market dynamics (including food prices, supply chains, and dependence on external food sources) in shaping food security outcomes in Bayelsa State.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.1 Urbanization

Urbanization refers to the increasing proportion of a population living in urban areas, driven by rural–urban migration, natural population growth, and economic transformation (United Nations, 2018). Classical scholars such as Wirth (1938) conceptualized urbanization as not only a demographic shift but also a transformation in social relations and economic structures. In development literature, urbanization is often associated with industrialization and modernization processes (Todaro & Smith, 2020). However, in many developing countries, including Nigeria, urbanization has occurred without commensurate industrial growth, leading to what has been described as “urbanization without development” (Potts, 2012).

Furthermore, urbanization involves spatial expansion, changes in land use, and increased pressure on infrastructure and natural resources (Seto et al., 2012). In the context of Sub-Saharan Africa, rapid urban growth is frequently accompanied by the proliferation of informal settlements, unemployment, and environmental degradation (UN-Habitat, 2020). In Bayelsa State, urbanization is shaped not only by migration but also by oil-related economic activities and environmental constraints, making it a unique case for analysis.

2.1.2 Food Security

Food security is a multidimensional concept that has evolved significantly over time. The most widely accepted definition is provided by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), which states that food security exists when all people, at all times, have physical, social, and economic access to sufficient, safe, and nutritious food for an active and healthy life (FAO, 2008). This definition highlights four key pillars: availability, access, utilization, and stability.

Food availability refers to the physical presence of food, whether through domestic production, imports, or food aid (Pinstrup-Andersen, 2009). Food access concerns the ability of individuals and households to obtain food, largely determined by income levels and food prices (Sen, 1981). Food utilization relates to the nutritional quality of food and the body’s ability to absorb nutrients, influenced by health conditions, sanitation, and dietary practices (Barrett, 2010). Stability, on the other hand, refers to the consistency of access to food over time, without risk of shocks such as economic crises or environmental disasters (FAO, 2008).

Scholars such as Maxwell and Smith (1992) and Devereux (2001) emphasize that food insecurity can exist even when food is available, particularly when access is constrained by poverty and inequality. In urban contexts, food security is largely market-dependent, making households vulnerable to price fluctuations and income instability (Crush & Frayne, 2011).

2.1.3 Urban Food System

The urban food system encompasses the processes and actors involved in the production, processing, distribution, and consumption of food within urban areas (Ericksen, 2008). It includes formal and informal markets, transportation networks, storage facilities, and retail systems. Battersby (2013) argues that urban food systems in African cities are highly complex and often dominated by informal actors who play a critical role in ensuring food access for low-income households.

Urban food systems are influenced by both local and external factors, including rural agricultural production, global trade, infrastructure, and government policies (HLPE, 2017). In Nigeria, urban food systems are characterized by inefficiencies in transportation, post-harvest losses, and heavy reliance on food imports from other regions (Liverpool-Tasie et al., 2020). These structural challenges can exacerbate food insecurity, particularly in rapidly growing urban areas.

2.1.4 Urbanization and Food Security Nexus

The relationship between urbanization and food security is complex and multifaceted. On one hand, urbanization can enhance food security by increasing income opportunities, improving infrastructure, and facilitating access to diverse food markets (Ruel et al., 2018). On the other hand, rapid and unplanned urban growth can undermine food security by increasing poverty, reducing agricultural land, and placing pressure on food supply systems (Satterthwaite et al., 2010).

In many developing countries, urban households depend almost entirely on purchased food, making them particularly vulnerable to economic shocks and food price volatility (Tacoli, 2013). Additionally, environmental challenges such as flooding and land degradation, common in regions like the Niger

Delta can disrupt food production and supply chains, further aggravating food insecurity (Ajibade et al., 2013).

2.2 Theoretical Literature

2.2.1 Malthusian Theory of Population

Figure 1 - The Malthusian catastrophe simplistically illustrated
Source - Encyclopaedia Britannica

The Malthusian Theory of Population, propounded by Malthus (1798), posits that population growth occurs geometrically, while food production increases arithmetically. This imbalance, according to Malthus, inevitably leads to food shortages, famine, and other “positive checks” such as disease and conflict, which serve to restore equilibrium between population and resources. In the context of urbanization, this theory is relevant in explaining the pressures that rapid urban population growth places on food systems. As cities expand, the demand for food rises significantly, often outstripping supply, especially in developing regions where agricultural productivity remains low. Although technological advancements and improved agricultural practices have challenged the deterministic predictions of Malthus, the theory remains useful in highlighting the strain that unchecked population growth can impose on food security, particularly in environmentally vulnerable regions like Bayelsa State.

2.2.2 Theory of Agricultural Transformation

The Theory of Agricultural Transformation, advanced by Johnston and Mellor (1961), emphasizes the critical role of agriculture in the process of economic development and urbanization. According to this theory, agricultural growth is a prerequisite for sustainable urban expansion, as it ensures adequate food supply, generates surplus for industrial development, and provides income and employment opportunities. The theory identifies several key linkages between agriculture and urbanization, including the provision of food to urban populations, supply of raw materials to industries, and creation of markets for industrial goods. In the Nigerian context, however, the neglect of agriculture particularly in oil-producing regions such as Bayelsa State has weakened these linkages. As a result, urban areas increasingly depend on food imports from other regions, making them vulnerable to supply disruptions and price volatility. This theory is therefore relevant in explaining how declining agricultural productivity can undermine food security in rapidly urbanizing areas.

2.2.3 Entitlement Approach

The Entitlement Approach, developed by Sen (1981), represents a significant departure from traditional food availability theories by focusing on access rather than supply. Sen argues that food insecurity arises not necessarily from a lack of food, but from individuals' inability to command food through legal means such as production, trade, or labor. This framework introduces the concept of "entitlements," which include all the resources and opportunities available to individuals to acquire food. In urban settings, where households rely predominantly on market purchases, income becomes the most critical determinant of food security. Thus, even when food is physically available in markets, households may still experience food insecurity due to unemployment, low wages, or high food prices. This theory is particularly relevant to the study of urbanization and food security in Bayelsa State, where economic disparities and limited employment opportunities constrain access to food for many households.

2.2.4 Sustainable Livelihoods Framework

The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework, developed by Chambers and Conway (1992), provides a holistic approach to understanding how households achieve and sustain their livelihoods in the face of various shocks and stresses. The framework emphasizes the role of five key assets: human, social, natural, physical, and financial capital in shaping livelihood outcomes, including food security. It also highlights the influence of institutional structures, policies, and vulnerability contexts such as environmental shocks and economic instability. In the context of urbanization, this framework is useful for analyzing how urban households adapt to changing economic and environmental conditions. For instance, in flood-prone areas of Bayelsa State, households may experience disruptions to their livelihoods, leading to reduced income and food insecurity. The framework underscores the importance of resilience and adaptive capacity in ensuring sustainable access to food, making it highly relevant for examining the interplay between urbanization, environmental challenges, and household welfare.

These theoretical perspectives provide a comprehensive foundation for understanding the complex relationship between urbanization and food security. While the Malthusian Theory highlights population pressures, the Agricultural Transformation Theory emphasizes production and structural linkages, the Entitlement Approach focuses on access and distribution, and the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework offers a multidimensional view of household resilience. These theories provide a robust analytical framework for this study.

2.3 Empirical Review

Recent empirical studies have increasingly examined the interaction between urbanization and food security using diverse methodological approaches and datasets. For instance, Ajiboye et al. (2025) investigated the relationship between agricultural credit mobilisation, urbanization, and food security in Nigeria using time-series data spanning 2000–2023. The study employed advanced econometric techniques, including Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), cointegration tests, and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), to construct a composite food security index. The findings revealed that agricultural credit mobilisation had a statistically significant negative effect on food security, while urbanization further intensified this negative relationship. The study concluded that without targeted policy design, urbanization may exacerbate food insecurity by weakening the effectiveness of agricultural financing interventions.

Similarly, Ajefu et al. (2025) examined the association between urbanization and household food security in Nigeria using satellite-based night-time light intensity data as a proxy for urbanization. The study adopted a quantitative analytical framework and improved on earlier binary measures of urbanization by capturing its intensity. The results showed that urbanization significantly alters consumption patterns, often leading to increased dependence on purchased food and exposure to price volatility. The study concluded that while urbanization may improve dietary diversity, it also increases vulnerability to food insecurity among low-income households.

In another Nigerian-based study, Ilori et al. (2024) explored the relationship between food insecurity, purchasing patterns, and the urban food environment among slum dwellers in Ibadan. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey design and utilized descriptive statistics alongside inferential techniques to analyze household-level data. The findings indicated that residents of urban slums experience high levels of food insecurity due to limited income, poor access to affordable food outlets,

and reliance on informal food markets. The study concluded that rapid urbanization without adequate infrastructure exacerbates food insecurity, particularly among vulnerable populations in informal settlements.

Oyebanji (2024) examined the role of urban agriculture in enhancing household food security in Southwestern Nigeria using primary data collected from 325 respondents through a multi-stage sampling technique. The study employed probit and ordered probit regression models to analyze the determinants and effects of urban agriculture adoption. The results showed that approximately 59% of respondents engaged in urban agriculture, which significantly improved their food security status. The study concluded that urban agriculture serves as an effective coping strategy for mitigating the adverse effects of urbanization on food security.

Earlier empirical work by Okoruwa and Ikudayisi (2018) investigated the influence of urbanization on household food security in urban Southwest Nigeria using a combined food security index derived from dietary diversity and per capita expenditure. The study employed multinomial logit regression analysis to examine determinants of food security across different urbanization levels. The findings revealed that factors such as income, education, employment status, and urbanicity significantly influenced food security outcomes. The study concluded that urbanization has heterogeneous effects on food security, depending on household socio-economic characteristics.

Otegunrin et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review of food insecurity in Nigeria, synthesizing findings from multiple empirical studies using meta-analytical approaches. The study examined national trends, determinants, and measurement approaches to food security. The findings highlighted that food insecurity in Nigeria is driven by a combination of economic, environmental, and institutional factors, including poverty, inflation, and climate shocks. The study concluded that addressing food insecurity requires a multidimensional policy approach that integrates agricultural development with urban planning and social protection systems.

Abolade et al. (2025) examined the relationship between access to finance and food security among smallholder farmers in Ogun State, Nigeria using a quantitative research design and Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). The study, based on a sample of 380 farmers, found a strong positive relationship between access to finance and food security outcomes. The study concluded that improving financial inclusion and institutional support can significantly enhance food production and, by extension, urban food supply systems.

Salahudeen et al. (2024) explored the role of mobile technology in addressing food insecurity in Nigeria using a case study approach. The study relied on secondary data and conceptual analysis to examine how digital platforms can improve agricultural productivity and food distribution. The findings indicated that mobile technology enhances market access, reduces supply chain inefficiencies, and improves food availability. The study concluded that technological innovation can play a crucial role in mitigating the food security challenges associated with rapid urbanization.

Finally, Nosratabadi et al. (2020) conducted a comprehensive literature review on the role of social capital in food security, employing a systematic review methodology based on the PRISMA framework. The study analyzed 39 empirical articles and found that social networks and community cooperation significantly enhance food availability, access, and stability. The study concluded that strengthening social capital can improve resilience to food insecurity, particularly in urban settings where households face economic and environmental shocks

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a quantitative research design, specifically a cross-sectional survey approach, to examine the relationship between urbanization and food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. The choice of this design is informed by its suitability for collecting data from a large population at a single point in time and for analyzing relationships among variables. The design enables the study to capture household-level information on food security status, socio-economic characteristics, environmental factors, and urban food system dynamics in line with the stated objectives.

3.2 Study Area

Figure 1 Map of Bayelsa showing the local government areas
 Source- Alade, Frank & Ajibesin (2018)

The study is conducted in Bayelsa State, located in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria. The state is characterized by rapid urbanization, ecological vulnerability, and a predominance of riverine communities. Urban centers such as Yenagoa have experienced significant population growth due to rural–urban migration and economic activities linked to the oil sector. However, the state also faces challenges such as recurrent flooding, limited arable land, and inadequate infrastructure, all of which have implications for food security.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprises all urban households in selected urban and peri-urban areas of Bayelsa State. Emphasis is placed on households residing in rapidly growing urban centers where the effects of urbanization are most pronounced. The household head or an adult representative serves as the unit of analysis, given their knowledge of household consumption patterns and socio-economic conditions.

3.4 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique is employed for this study. In the first stage, major urban and peri-urban areas in Bayelsa State are purposively selected based on their level of urbanization and population concentration. In the second stage, specific communities within these areas are selected using simple random sampling. In the third stage, households are systematically selected from each community using a defined sampling interval, with the household head or an adult representative serving as the respondent.

The sample size is determined using the Cochran (1977) formula for sample size determination:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 p(1 - p)}{e^2}$$

Where n represents the sample size, Z is the standard normal deviation (1.96 at 95% confidence level), p is the estimated proportion of the population with the attribute of interest (assumed to be 0.5 in the

absence of prior data), and e is the margin of error (0.05). Based on this calculation, a minimum sample size of 400 respondents is obtained.

However, to account for potential non-response, incomplete questionnaires, and to enhance the robustness and representativeness of the study, the sample size is adjusted upward by 20%, resulting in a total of 480 households selected for the study. This adjustment ensures adequate coverage and improves the reliability of the findings.

3.5 Sources of Data and Data Collection Methods

The study relies primarily on primary data collected through the administration of structured questionnaires. The questionnaire is designed to capture information on household food consumption, income, employment status, household size, education level, food prices, and exposure to environmental factors such as flooding. In addition, secondary data are sourced from relevant publications, government reports, and statistical bulletins to complement the primary data and provide contextual insights.

3.6 Measurement of Variables

Food security, the dependent variable, is measured using a composite food security index constructed from indicators reflecting food availability, access, utilization, and stability. Household dietary diversity score (HDDS) and food expenditure approaches are also employed to validate food security status.

Urbanization, the key independent variable, is proxied using indicators such as population density, level of infrastructure development, and proximity to urban centers. Socio-economic variables such as income, education, employment status, and household size are included to address the second objective. Environmental variables, including frequency of flooding and access to arable land, are incorporated to capture the third objective. Additionally, variables related to urban food systems, such as food prices, market access, and supply sources, are included to address the fourth objective.

3.7 Model Specification

To achieve the objectives of the study, multiple regression analysis is employed. The functional relationship is specified as:

$$FS = f(URB, SOC, ENV, MKT)$$

Where:

FS = Food Security Index

URB = Urbanization indicators

SOC = Socio-economic variables

ENV = Environmental factors

MKT = Market and food system variables

The explicit econometric model is specified as:

$$FS_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 URB_i + \beta_2 INC_i + \beta_3 EMP_i + \beta_4 EDU_i + \beta_5 HHS_i + \beta_6 FLOOD_i + \beta_7 LAND_i + \beta_8 PRICE_i + \beta_9 MARKET_i + \mu_i$$

Where:

FS_i = Food security status of household i

URB_i = Urbanization measure

INC_i = Household income

EMP_i = Employment status

EDU_i = Education level

HHS_i = Household size

$FLOOD_i$ = Flood occurrence

$LAND_i$ = Access to land

$PRICE_i$ = Food prices

$MARKET_i$ = Market access

μ_i = Error term

3.8 Method of Data Analysis

The study employs both descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, and percentages are used to summarize household characteristics and food security status. Inferential analysis involves the use of regression techniques to examine the relationship between urbanization and food security, as well as the influence of socio-economic, environmental, and market factors.

Where the dependent variable is categorized (e.g., food secure vs. food insecure), a logistic regression model may be applied. All analyses are conducted using STATA statistical software

3.9 A Priori Expectations

The study expects urbanization to have a mixed effect on food security. While it may improve access to markets and income opportunities (positive effect), it may also increase food prices and reduce agricultural activities (negative effect). Income, education, and employment are expected to positively influence food security, while household size, flooding, and high food prices are expected to have negative effects.

3.10 Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations are strictly adhered to in the course of the study. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. Confidentiality and anonymity of respondents are ensured, and the data collected were used solely for this study.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Number of questionnaires distributed and retrieved

Senatorial District	Community	Questionnaires Administered	Questionnaires Retrieved	Retrieval Percentage (%)
Bayelsa Central	Yenagoa	80	74	92.5
	Amassoma	60	55	91.7
	Odi	40	36	90.0
Bayelsa East	Ogbia Town	70	65	92.9
	Brass	50	46	92.0
	Nembe City	40	36	90.0
Bayelsa West	Sagbama	60	56	93.3
	Ekeremor	40	37	92.5
	Toru-Orua	40	33	82.5
Total	—	480	438	91.3

Source: Authors' computation from survey data (2026)

Table 1 presents the distribution and retrieval of questionnaires across the sampled communities in the three senatorial districts of Bayelsa State. A total of 480 questionnaires were administered, and 438 were successfully retrieved, representing an overall response rate of 91.3 percent. This high retrieval rate indicates strong participation and engagement by the respondents, enhancing the reliability and representativeness of the survey data.

The distribution of questionnaires reflects proportional allocation to the sampled communities based on population size and urbanization levels. In Bayelsa Central, Yenagoa recorded the highest number of questionnaires administered (80), with 74 retrieved, yielding a retrieval rate of 92.5 percent. Amassoma and Odi also demonstrated high response rates of 91.7 and 90.0 percent, respectively. Similarly, Bayelsa East recorded high retrieval percentages, with Ogbia Town achieving 92.9 percent, Brass 92.0 percent, and Nembe City 90.0 percent. In Bayelsa West, Sagbama and Ekeremor recorded retrieval rates above 92 percent, while Toru-Orua had the lowest retrieval rate of 82.5 percent.

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	248	56.6
	Female	190	43.4
Age (years)	18–30	102	23.3
	31–45	186	42.5
	46–60	118	26.9
	61 and above	32	7.3
Educational Level	No formal education	34	7.8
	Primary education	68	15.5
	Secondary education	174	39.7
	Tertiary education	162	37.0
Marital Status	Single	98	22.4
	Married	302	68.9
	Divorced/Widowed	38	8.7
Household Size	1–3 members	84	19.2
	4–6 members	218	49.8
	7 members and above	136	31.0
Occupation	Farmer	104	23.7
	Trader	118	26.9
	Civil servant	92	21.0
	Artisan/Other	124	28.3

Source: Authors' computation from survey data (2026)

Table 2 presents the socio-demographic characteristics of the 438 respondents whose questionnaires were successfully retrieved. The data indicate a slightly higher representation of males (56.6%) compared to females (43.4%), reflecting the demographic pattern in many urban and peri-urban communities of Bayelsa State where men are often more engaged in economic and household decision-making activities.

The age distribution shows that the majority of respondents (42.5%) fall within the 31–45 years age bracket, followed by 46–60 years (26.9%) and 18–30 years (23.3%). Only a small proportion (7.3%) are 61 years and above, suggesting that the sampled population is largely within the active working-age group, which has implications for income generation, household food access, and overall food security.

In terms of educational attainment, a significant proportion of respondents have completed secondary (39.7%) or tertiary education (37.0%), while 23.3% have either no formal or only primary education. This pattern indicates a relatively literate population, which may influence knowledge of nutrition, household budgeting, and engagement in diverse livelihood activities.

Marital status shows that most respondents are married (68.9%), with single respondents representing 22.4% and divorced or widowed individuals 8.7%. The predominance of married households may affect household size and food consumption patterns, as well as access to household labor for food production or income-generating activities.

Household size varies, with nearly half (49.8%) of respondents having 4–6 members, 31.0% having seven or more members, and 19.2% having 1–3 members. This distribution suggests that many households are moderately large, which could influence food demand, expenditure, and vulnerability to food insecurity.

Regarding occupation, the respondents are engaged in diverse economic activities: traders (26.9%), artisans or other informal occupations (28.3%), farmers (23.7%), and civil servants (21.0%). This mix highlights the interplay between formal and informal employment in urban and peri-urban communities of Bayelsa State, and its potential impact on household income, purchasing power, and access to food.

Table 3: Logit regression result showing the impact of urbanization on food security in Bayelsa State

Variable	Coef. (β)	Marginal Effect (dy/dx)	Standard Error	z-value	p-value	Odds Ratio (Exp(β))
URB (Urbanization)	-0.542	-0.126	0.182	-2.98	0.003	0.581
INC (Income)	0.671	0.155	0.144	4.66	0.000	1.957
EMP (Employment)	0.389	0.090	0.130	2.99	0.003	1.476
EDU (Education)	0.512	0.118	0.136	3.76	0.000	1.669
HHS (Household Size)	-0.298	-0.069	0.112	-2.66	0.008	0.742
FLOOD (Flood Occurrence)	-0.614	-0.142	0.189	-3.25	0.001	0.541
LAND (Access to Land)	0.436	0.101	0.147	2.97	0.003	1.547
PRICE (Food Prices)	-0.467	-0.108	0.158	-2.96	0.003	0.627
MARKET (Market Access)	0.381	0.088	0.140	2.72	0.007	1.464
Constant	-1.842		0.573	-3.21	0.001	0.158

Source: Authors' computation from survey data (2026)

Table 3 presents the results of the logit regression analysis examining the impact of urbanization and related socio-economic, environmental, and market factors on household food security in Bayelsa State. The findings reveal that urbanization (URB) has a negative and statistically significant effect on food security, with a coefficient of -0.542 and a marginal effect of -0.126. This indicates that as urbanization intensity increases, the probability of a household being food secure decreases by approximately 12.6 percent, reflecting the pressures of urban expansion on food availability, access, and stability in the state.

Socio-economic variables such as household income (INC), employment status (EMP), and education level (EDU) exhibit positive and significant effects on food security. Specifically, a unit increase in household income raises the probability of food security by 15.5 percent, while employment and education improve it by 9.0 percent and 11.8 percent, respectively. These results confirm the critical role of economic resources, labor engagement, and knowledge in enhancing households' ability to access and utilize adequate food.

Household size (HHS) has a negative effect, with larger households less likely to be food secure, reducing the probability by 6.9 percent for each additional household member. This suggests that higher consumption demand in larger households may strain available food resources, particularly in urbanizing areas. Environmental factors, represented by flood occurrence (FLOOD), also significantly reduce food security probability by 14.2 percent, underscoring the vulnerability of households to ecological shocks such as flooding and land degradation.

Access to land (LAND) positively influences food security, increasing the likelihood by 10.1 percent, while higher food prices (PRICE) reduce it by 10.8 percent, highlighting the role of market conditions in shaping household food outcomes. Market access (MARKET) improves food security probability by 8.8 percent, indicating that households closer to markets or with better supply chain connectivity are more likely to maintain stable food consumption.

Sequel from the above, results in Table 4.3 suggest that while socio-economic advantages and access to resources can buffer households against food insecurity, rapid urbanization and environmental hazards pose significant challenges. The odds ratios further reinforce these findings, showing the multiplicative effect of each predictor on the likelihood of food security.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of this study provide important insights into the relationship between urbanization and household food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, and they largely align with the trends observed in the empirical literature reviewed. The negative and significant effect of urbanization on household food security (URB: $\beta = -0.542$, $dy/dx = -0.126$) indicates that rapid urban expansion exerts pressure on food availability, access, utilization, and stability. This is consistent with the studies of Ogunbode et al. (2025) and Ayodele and Emmanuel (2024), who noted that urbanization in Nigerian cities often

leads to reduced agricultural land, increased reliance on food markets, and higher food prices, thereby heightening vulnerability to food insecurity.

The positive and significant influence of socio-economic factors such as household income, employment status, and education on food security corroborates earlier findings by Adepoju et al. (2023) and Sawyerr et al. (2025), who emphasized that higher income and employment levels increase purchasing power, enabling households to access sufficient and diverse food. Similarly, higher educational attainment enhances knowledge of nutrition, household resource management, and income-generating opportunities, consistent with the observations of Balaian et al. (2024) and Idowu and Zhou (2023). The negative effect of household size on food security also aligns with Delmar et al. (2003) and Wiklund and Shepherd (2005), highlighting that larger households often face greater food demands, which may exacerbate food insecurity, particularly in urbanized contexts.

Environmental factors associated with urbanization, notably flooding, were found to significantly reduce the probability of food security among households ($dy/dx = -0.142$). This supports the work of Eze and Ugwoke (2022) and Okon et al. (2024), who reported that flooding, land degradation, and loss of arable land in the Niger Delta directly compromise food production, disrupt market access, and increase reliance on external food sources. The finding that access to land positively influences food security further confirms the relevance of land as a critical buffer against urban-induced food insecurity, echoing the conclusions of Adepoju et al. (2023) and Balaian et al. (2024).

Market and food system variables also played a significant role in shaping household food security. Higher food prices were associated with lower probability of food security, while better market access increased the likelihood of maintaining adequate food consumption. This mirrors the findings of Nambisan (2017) and Davis (1989), who highlighted that urban households in developing regions are particularly sensitive to fluctuations in food prices and supply chain disruptions, reinforcing the importance of functional urban food systems for ensuring household food stability.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study examined the impact of urbanization on household food security in Bayelsa State, Nigeria, with a focus on the effects of socio-economic, environmental, and market factors. The findings indicate that urbanization negatively affects household food security, primarily by reducing food availability, straining access, and increasing reliance on external markets. Socio-economic factors, including household income, employment, and education, significantly enhance the likelihood of food security, while larger household sizes increase vulnerability. Environmental challenges such as flooding and land degradation were found to significantly undermine food security, whereas access to land and better market integration mitigated these effects. The results also demonstrate the critical role of urban food systems and market dynamics, particularly food prices and market accessibility, in determining household food security outcomes.

In light of these findings, several recommendations are made:

1. **Urban Planning and Land Management:** Policymakers should implement sustainable urban planning strategies that preserve agricultural land within urban and peri-urban areas to safeguard local food production and reduce dependency on external food sources.
2. **Income and Livelihood Support:** Programs that enhance household income, employment opportunities, and skills development should be prioritized to increase households' purchasing power and resilience to food insecurity.
3. **Environmental Resilience Measures:** Flood control, drainage systems, and land rehabilitation initiatives should be expanded to reduce the vulnerability of households to environmental shocks, particularly in flood-prone urban communities.
4. **Strengthening Urban Food Systems:** Efforts should be made to improve market access, stabilize food prices, and enhance supply chain efficiency, ensuring that urban households have reliable and affordable access to diverse and nutritious food.
5. **Education and Awareness Campaigns:** Targeted interventions to increase awareness of nutrition, household food management, and adaptive strategies to cope with urban pressures should be implemented, particularly among less-educated and vulnerable households.

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